

COMPARATIVE ASSESSMENT OF *STAPHYLOCOCCUS AUREUS* STUDIED USING TWO METHODS AS PART OF CREATING AN EXTERNAL QUALITY ASSESSMENT PANEL

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Abstract. *The quality of laboratory diagnostics depends on the correct performance of procedures at all stages of laboratory testing. The evaluation and quality of laboratory processes can also be ensured through the implementation and regular annual conduct of external quality assessment (EQA) programs. Currently, there is no organization in the republic responsible for conducting EQA. In this regard, our laboratory set the objective of developing a panel for EQA. One of the strains included in the panel is Staphylococcus aureus. To study the stability of antimicrobial susceptibility and resistance properties, 42 strains of S. aureus were selected. After five repeated assessments of strain stability using two methods, including storage at –80°C, as well as three additional assessments after lyophilization, four strains (9.5%) demonstrating stable properties were selected.*

Keywords: *stability of properties, external quality assessment, panel.*

Introduction

Currently, one of the urgent tasks in public health is the qualitative diagnosis of a number of infectious diseases of bacterial etiology. Despite a series of measures aimed at improving epidemiological supervision and the prevention of purulent bacterial infections, the incidence of many infections remains high.

One of the main problems of practical healthcare remains infections with multiple resistance to antimicrobial drugs. The percentage of pathogenic and conditionally pathogenic bacterial strains possessing multi-resistance to antibiotics is increasing; infection pathogens cause not only purulent-septic complications after surgery and injections but also pneumonia, urological, and acute intestinal infections [2, 6, 4].

Due to its ability to adapt to changing environmental conditions and various life-threatening infections, *Staphylococcus aureus* is one of the most complex pathogens, particularly to the action of antimicrobial drugs. According to the Health Protection Agency, during the period from 1997 to 2005, the frequency of *S. aureus* isolation was 41.4% in the development of surgical intervention area infection. It is known that the natural sensitivity of staphylococci to the vast majority of antibacterial drugs is quite high. Despite this, antibacterial therapy can pose a serious problem due to the formation of antibiotic resistance in microorganisms and their ability to form microbial bioplots on the surface of implants [14].

The most difficult to treat are infections caused by methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* (MRSA) and *S. epidermidis* (MRSE). The widespread prevalence of MRSA and the frequency of its

detection are constantly increasing: in the USA in 2000, the frequency of MRSA isolation in intensive care units was 53%, which is 29% higher than the similar figure for the period 1995–1999 [10, 1].

Clinical test results obtained in laboratories or testing centers at or near medical care facilities must be as accurate as possible, as they have a direct impact on care and treatment, prevention, and disease control [5].

The quality of laboratory diagnostics depends on both the pre-analytical stage—taking and delivering pathological material—and the analytical stage—the culture study conducted in microbiological laboratories [3].

The term “external quality assessment” (EQA) is used to describe a method/process that allows for the comparison of testing conducted by a laboratory, testing station, or individual user with testing conducted outside this laboratory, for example, by a group of similar laboratories, a reference laboratory, or a testing station. The successful participation of a testing station in the EQA program provides clients, accrediting, and regulatory bodies with objective data on the qualification of the testing service and serves as a unique source of information that is difficult to obtain by other means [12, 7].

It is important to note that participation in the EQA program allows for a “partnership audit” of the process to address technical and methodological issues in order to improve service quality at each individual testing point, as well as to ensure the comparability of results between various services providing diagnostic services. The EQA provides objective data on the quality of services provided to accrediting and regulatory bodies and, as demonstrated, reflects the quality of patient sample testing [13, 9].

In most developed countries, EQA programs are reliably developed and significantly contribute to improving the quality of medical care at all levels of the healthcare system [11, 8], but in our country, there is no system that conducts EQA for bacteriological laboratories.

In this regard, we have set a goal to identify the most stable strains of *S. aureus* to create a EQA panel.

Materials and methods

The study was conducted within the framework of the Cooperation Agreement between the Center and the Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center for Epidemiology, Microbiology, Infectious and Parasitic Diseases (RSSPMCEMIPD) under project No. 5 NU2HGH000089-04-00 "Expanding the surveillance epidemiological surveillance network to counter the problem of resistance to antimicrobial drugs in the Republic of Uzbekistan."

S. aureus strains were identified and studied for sensitivity to antimicrobial drugs in the Reference Laboratory of the Center for Antimicrobial Resistance (CAMR) of the RSSPMCEMIPD. Identification of strains was performed using the PID (REF) -448008 panels of the BD Phoenix (USA) bacteriological analyzer.

Sensitivity and interpretation of antimicrobial sensitivity test (AMS) results were conducted using two methods, the disc-diffusion method, using the guidelines of the European Committee for the Determination of Sensitivity to Antimicrobial Drugs (EUCAST 2023). The sensitivity of all strains to 9 antibacterial drugs was determined: cefoxitin (FOX), penicillin (PEN), ciprofloxacin (CIP), levofloxacin (LVX), erythromycin (ERY), clindamycin (CLI), linezolid (LNZ), rifampicin (RIF), and amikacin (AMK), manufactured by Liofilchelm, Italy. *S. aureus* AST was also studied in parallel using PMIC-600 (REF) -449055 panels from the BD Phoenix bacteriological analyzer, manufactured in the USA. To monitor the quality of the conducted

studies, reference strains of *Staphylococcus aureus* NCTC 12973 were used. The obtained sensitivity results were processed using the WHONET and Microsoft Excel programs. Lyophilic drying was carried out on the INFITEK LYO60B-1S apparatus, which includes several stages. The LYO60B-1S sublimation dryer utilizes extremely low temperatures (-60°C) and vacuum to remove moisture from microorganisms. Lyophilic drying was carried out in penicillin vials with a smooth neck, in a volume of 10 ml. The lyophilization process: in the first stage, the biomaterial was frozen to a temperature of minus 60 °C. In the second stage, primary drying occurs, where all frozen free moisture is sublimated under the influence of vacuum and thermal energy. The third stage is the final drying of the product, when the remaining moisture is removed. The lyophilization process takes 18-22 hours.

Results and discussion

To form a EQA panel, the stability of antimicrobial sensitivity properties was studied for 41 strains of *S. aureus* and one control strain of *S. aureus* NCTC 12973. All strains were identified as *S. aureus*.

To study the stability of the sensitivity-resistance properties of *S. aureus* strains to antimicrobial drugs, at the initial stage, strains stored frozen at a temperature of minus 80°C were studied. Each strain was tested five times (1 month, 2 months, 3 months, 6 months, and 1 year) before lyophilic drying, as well as one month, 3 months, and 6 months after lyophilic drying. The results of the AST data were analyzed for the stability of strain sensitivity-resistance properties to antimicrobial drugs.

The disc-diffusion method is the primary method for determining sensitivity to antimicrobial drugs in most clinical microbiological laboratories. The composition of the antibiotic panel is flexible and allows the clinical laboratory to easily modify the panel according to its needs. However, this method has its own disadvantages, including labor costs associated with manual measurements and manual documentation of data, as well as dependence on the researcher and variability of results.

The first stage of the analysis to compare the stability of sensitivity-resistance results of *S. aureus* strains was the calculation of the mean values of the strain lysis range, in mm, relative to antimicrobial drugs (Table 1).

Table 1. Average index of the lysis range of *S. aureus* strains, in mm, relative to antimicrobial drugs

Antibiotic	<i>S. aureus</i> (n=42) (mm)					Reliability of Results
	In 1 month.	In 2 month.	In 4 month.	In 6 month.	After 1 year	
Benzylopenicillin P1	6,1±0,1	6,1±0,1	6,3±0,3	6,2±0,1	6,2±0,1	P≥0,05
Cefoxitin FOX 30	27,8±0,7	27,8±0,7	27,8±0,8	27,4±0,7	27,4±0,7	P≥0,05
Ciprofloxacin CIP 5	23,7±0,8	23,6±0,8	23,0±0,7	23,6±0,7	23,6±0,7	P≥0,05
Levofloxacin LEV 5	25,4±0,8	25,3±0,9	25,1±0,8	25,4±0,7	25,4±0,7	P≥0,05
Amikacin AK30	16,1±0,8	16,1±0,8	18,6±0,5	18,4±0,6	18,4±0,6	P≤0,05
Gentamicin CN 10	17,2±0,7	17,2±0,7	17,5±0,5	17,6±0,5	17,6±0,5	P≥0,05
Eritromycin E 15	18,9±1,3	19,0±1,3	14,9±1,4	14,9±1,4	14,9±1,4	P≤0,05
Clindamycin CD 2	19,6±1,3	19,7±1,3	18,1±1,4	18,4±1,3	18,1±1,4	P≥0,05

Linozolid LNL 10	27,3±0,4	27,3±0,4	26,3±0,2	26,3±0,2	26,3±0,2	P≤0,05
Rifampicin RD 5	29,8±0,8	29,8±0,8	29,4±0,6	29,4±0,6	29,4±0,6	P≥0,05

The results of the analysis of *S. aureus* strain resistance data show that the average sensitivity-resistance indicator to most tested antimicrobial drugs remains stable throughout the year. Table 1 presents the changes in resistance levels over various time intervals (1 month, 2 months, 4 months, 6 months, 1 year). Thus, we see that for most antibiotics (for example, P1, CIP 5, LEV 5, CN 10, LNL 10, RD 5), resistance values remain practically unchanged throughout the year. Minor fluctuations are observed in some antimicrobial drugs, such as AK30 and E 15, but the changes are statistically significant, which may be related to strain adaptation or technical measurement factors. Overall, the *S. aureus* strain presented in the study demonstrates high resistance to antimicrobial drugs during one year of storage.

Subsequently, we conducted an analysis of variance (ANOVA) to verify the presence of statistically significant differences between data groups representing changes in *S. aureus* resistance depending on storage time (Table 1). Analysis of data on the stability of *S. aureus* strain resistance differs in its results. Thus, by analyzing the stability results of strain resistance to ten antimicrobial drugs, we see that two antimicrobial drugs, P1 (100.0%) and CD2 (38.1%), maintain stable resistance when the culture is frozen at minus 80°C for one year.

Table 2. Analysis of sensitivity test data for antimicrobial drugs of *S. aureus* strains for property stability using the disc-diffusion method.

Antibiotic	<i>S. aureus</i> (n=42) (R)					F-value	p-value
	In 1 month.	In 2 month .	In 4 month.	In 6 month.	After 1 year		
Benzylpenicillin P1	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	0.000	1.00000
Cefoxitin FOX 30	14,3±5,4	14,3±5,4	16,7±5,8	16,7±5,8	16,7±5,8	0.737	0.57132
Ciprofloxacin CIP 5	9,5±4,5	9,5±4,5	11,9±5,0	7,1±4,0	7,1±4,0	0.697	0.58947
Levofloxacin LEV 5	9,5±4,5	9,5±4,5	11,9±5,0	9,5±4,5	9,5±4,5	0.500	0.73898
Amikacin AK30	35,7±7,4	38,1±7,5	7,1±4,0	9,5±4,5	9,5±4,5	6.245	0.00261**
Gentamicin CN 10	31,0±7,1	31,0±7,1	14,3±5,4	14,3±5,4	14,3±5,4	4.901	0.00964**
Eritromycin E 15	42,9±7,6	40,5±7,6	57,1±7,6	57,1±7,6	57,1±7,6	2.917	0.04783*
Clindamycin CD 2	38,1±7,5	38,1±7,5	38,1±7,5	38,1±7,5	38,1±7,5	0.000	1.00000
Linozolid LNL 10	2,4±2,4	2,4±2,4	0,00	0,00	0,00	9.760	0.00014***

Rifampicin RD 5	7,1±4,0	7,1±4,0	2,4±2,4	2,4±2,4	2,4±2,4	3.401	0.02867*
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Note: *p* ≤ 0.05, the changes are statistically significant (*); *p* ≤ 0.01, the changes are more significant (); *p* ≤ 0.001, the changes are highly significant (***); *p* > 0.05, the differences are not significant.

For other antimicrobial drugs, resistance values vary, with resistant strains increasing after three months of storage to FOX 30 from 14.29% to 16.67% and E 15 from 40.48% to 57.14%. Resistant strains decreased in *S. aureus* strains after 6 months of storage compared to CIP 5 from 14.29% to 7.14%, LNL 10 from 2.38% to 0.0%, and RD 5 from 7.14% to 2.38%. The indicators of resistant strains to LEV 5 were consistently the same at 9.52% throughout the year, with the exception of a one-time increase of 11.90% after three months.

Thus, resistance to AK30, CN 10, LNL 10 changed significantly (p < 0.01), for E 15 and RD 5 changes were moderately significant (p < 0.05), for P1 and CD 2 changes were insignificant (p = 1.000), indicating stability of resistance.

Due to the fact that the strain sensitivity data to antimicrobial drugs obtained by the disk-diffusion method differed, we placed AST on the PMIC-600 (REF) -449055 panel of the BD Phoenix bacteriological analyzer in parallel. Automatic microbiological systems have been developed for the rapid, reliable, and accurate identification of bacteria (ID) and testing for susceptibility to antimicrobial drugs (AST) for most clinically encountered species.

Table 3. Average minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of *S. aureus*, in mg/L, relative to antimicrobial drugs

Antibiotic	<i>S. aureus</i> (n=42) (mg/L)				p-value
	In 2 month	In 4 month.	In 6 month.	After 1 year	
Benzylpenicillin P1	0,4±0,03	0,4±0,02	0,3±0,03	0,4±0,02	P=1.00
Cefoxitin FOX 30	4,3±0,7	5,0±0,8	5,0±0,8	5,0±0,8	P=0.51
Ciprofloxacin CIP 5	1,1±0,1	1,1±0,1	1,1±0,1	1,1±0,1	P=1.00
Levofloxacin LEV 5	1,1±0,1	1,2±0,2	1,2±0,2	1,2±0,2	P=0.65
Amikacin AK30	5±0,4	6,6±0,3	5±0,3	5±0,3	P=1.00
Gentamicin CN 10	1,1±0,05	1,0±0,03	1,1±0,07	1,1±0,07	P=1.00
Eritromycin E 15	1,2±0,2	1,1±0,2	1,2±0,2	1,2±0,2	P=1.00
Clindamycin CD 2	0,3±0,01	0,3±0,01	0,3±0,01	0,3±0,01	P=1.00
Linzolid LNL 10	2,0±0,00	2,0±0,00	2,0±0,00	2,0±0,00	-
Rifampicin RD 5	0,3±0,01	0,3±0,00	0,2±0,01	0,2±0,01	-
Vancomycin	1,1±0,1	1,0±0,00	1,0±0,00	1,0±0,00	P=0.32
Daptomycin	1,1±0,07	1,0±0,00	1,0±0,00	1,0±0,00	P=0.15
Moxifloxacin 5	0,3±0,02	0,3±0,02	0,3±0,02	0,3±0,02	P=1.00
Oxacillin	0,9±0,2	1,0±0,2	1,0±0,2	1,0±0,2	P=0.72
Teicoplanin	1,1±0,07	1,1±0,07	1,1±0,07	1,1±0,07	P=1.00
Tetracycline 30	0,6±0,05	0,6±0,05	0,6±0,05	0,6±0,05	P=1.00

Trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole 1,25	2,1±0,1	2,1±0,1	2,1±0,1	2,1±0,1	P=1.00
Fosfomycin	8,2±0,2	9,0±0,4	9,0±0,6	9,0±0,6	P=0.2
Fusidic acid 10	1,0±0,00	1,0±0,00	1,0±0,00	1,0±0,00	-

Analysis results of the average values of the minimum inhibitory concentration of *S. aureus* strains show that for all tested antimicrobial drugs, the average MIC values remain the same throughout the year.

Table 4. Analysis of sensitivity test data for antimicrobial drugs of *S. aureus* strains for property stability using the PMIC-600 BD Phoenix panel.

Antibiotic	<i>S. aureus</i> (n=42) (R)				F-value	p-value
	In 2 month .	In 4 month.	In 6 month.	After 1 year		
Benzylpenicillin P1	100	100	100	100	0.000	1.00000
Ciprofloxacin CIP 5	4,8±3,3	4,8±3,3	4,8±3,3	4,8±3,3	0.000	1.00000
Levofloxacin LEV 5	4,8±3,3	4,8±3,3	4,8±3,3	4,8±3,3	0.000	1.00000
Amikacin AK30	2,4±2,4	0,00	0,00	0,00	2.000	0.14635
Gentamicin CN 10	11,9±5,0	4,8±3,3	4,8±3,3	4,8±3,3	3.570	0.04178*
Eritromycin E 15	23,8±6,6	21,4±6,3	23,8±6,6	23,8±6,6	1.732	0.19713
Clindamycin CD 2	14,3±5,4	21,4±6,3	7,1±4,0	21,4±6,3	3.214	0.05583
Linozolid LNL 10	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0.000	1.00000
Rifampicin RD 5	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0.000	1.00000
Vancomycin	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0.000	1.00000
Daptomycin	2,4±2,4	0,00	0,00	0,00	2.000	0.14635
Moxifloxacin 5	4,8±3,3	4,8±3,3	4,8±3,3	4,8±3,3	0.000	1.00000
Oxacillin	16,7±5,8	16,7±5,8	16,7±5,8	16,7±5,8	0.000	1.00000
Teicoplanin	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0.000	1.00000
Tetracycline 30	4,8±3,3	4,8±3,3	4,8±3,3	4,8±3,3	0.000	1.00000
Trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole 1,25	4,8±3,3	4,8±3,3	4,8±3,3	4,8±3,3	0.000	1.00000
Fosfomycin	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0.000	1.00000
Fusidic acid 10	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0.000	1.00000

Analyzing the data using dispersion analysis (ANOVA), the stability of sensitivity and resistance of *S. aureus* strains using the PMIC-600 BD Phoenix panel, we see (Table. 2) that out of nineteen antimicrobial drugs proposed by the manufacturer in the panel, the sensitivity-resistance values for fourteen antimicrobial drugs were maintained at all stages of the research. Regarding other antimicrobial drugs, a decrease in the occurrence of resistant strains is observed; thus, a more pronounced decrease in resistance indicators is observed for antimicrobial drugs of the aminoglycoside series; for AK from 2.4% to 0.0%, and for CN 10 from 11.9% to 4.8%.

Resistance to CN 10 changed significantly ($p < 0.05$), while for most antibiotics the changes were not significant, indicating stability of resistance.

After analyzing the stability of susceptibility–resistance of *S. aureus* strains using two methods, we selected 8 *S. aureus* strains for lyophilization and further study of their stability. Following lyophilization, a three-time assessment (after 1 month, 3 months, and 6 months) was conducted to evaluate the stability of susceptibility–resistance characteristics.

Based on the analysis of the obtained data, four strains were selected for the creation of the EQA panel, as they did not change their properties throughout the entire study period.

Conclusion

The EQA program allows for a “peer review” of the process to address technical and methodological issues with the aim of improving the quality of service at each individual testing site, as well as ensuring the comparability of results between different diagnostic service providers. In this regard, the panel of strains being developed by us must have stable properties to accurately assess the competence of staff and the quality of the conducted research, particularly the antimicrobial susceptibility testing of the laboratories involved.

Research on the stability of *S. aureus* strains showed that not all strains maintain their properties during storage. Only 9.5% of *S. aureus* strains retained their properties and were selected for the creation of the panel.

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